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DIGITAL BRUSH WITH INTUITIVE OPERATION DESIGN FOR CHILDREN ON TANGIBLE USER INTERFACE

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ABSTRACT

This research works around intuitive operation, integrating the concept of Tangible User Interface (TUI) to discuss an intuitive operating method of digital drawing brushes suitable for children 4-7 years old. We put into consideration the requirements and cognitive ability of children, coordinating the tactile and visual learning of children during this specific phase, and using shapes to communicate the default functions. By recognizing different lines, observing 3D shapes, and intuitively changing brush strokes, we have enriched the lines and maintained the values of conventional drawing in digital drawing.

Experiment results show that (1) Children are able to feel the lines and the form through tactile and visual senses. (2) The stroke application is much more versatile in intuitive operation as compared to visual icon interfaces. (3) The objective meter table shows that children obtain higher pleasure with intuitive tangible digital brushes, increasing their incentive to continue using them.

Keywords: Intuitive operation, Digital brush, Tangible user interface (TUI).

INTRODUCTION

Drawings are the projection of children's mental activities and experience. From drawings we can pry into children's cognitive, beauty, social, and creativity developments. During recent years, drawing has been employed to collect information on suggestions for computer software for children and to employ as reference for academic curriculum and computer technology (Xu, Read, Sim, & McManus, 2009).

Most children draw with conventional paper and brushes. Conventional drawing stimulates imagination and creativity, trains hand muscles, and

build a healthy character development through expressing emotions with drawings. Nevertheless, come the digital era, digital drawing has become common in our lives. The current digital drawing device platforms for professionals and artists, such as I Love Sketch employs pen gesture definition to control 3D rotation and color presentation (Bae, Balakrishnan, & Singh, 2008). INKTUITIVE employs infrared technology to track hand movements. Users are able to create with tangible drawing paper. The camera tracks the procedures and digitalizes the tangible physical drawings and process through computer calculating to simulate the model (Mistry, Sekiya, & Bradshaw, 2008). VoodooSketch drawing system allows users to arrange visible or drawn electronic components, creating a personalized color mixing tray (Block, Haller, Gellersen, Gutwin, & Billingham, 2008). The Hong Kong University of Technology designed a new type of digital brush, using the sensor nodes inside the brush, simulating the bending and stretching movements of a genuine brush, as well as the effect of a semi-dry brush (Chu, 2004). Other research focusing on children digital drawing include Jabberstamp integrating child drawings with voices (Raffle, Vaucelle, Wang, & Ishii, 2007), I/O brush employing a camera to capture any motionless or moving images allowing users to brush on to the screen (Ryokai, Marti, & Ishii, 2004), and KIDPAD providing multiple interaction, through zooming elements on a screen to create dynamic movements between story structure parts in order to give children the chance to create a non-linear story. The current research directions have the conventional drawing experience of simulated users as their goals. When children draw on with conventional paper and brushes, they often show interesting images with their stroke line variations. Children between 4 to 7 years old are in the

preoperational period of their recognition development stages and often intuitively create images. Their drawing development is in the stage of post-icon period (Hu, Po-Lin, 1986). During this period, children use lines to express their images. In the use of digital drawing, there is insufficient research on the stroke manner consideration of children. Hence, this research focuses on the concept of intuitive operation, using Tangible User Interface (TUI), allowing children to use their intuitions to operate and use digital brushes with ease. Children are able to use their past drawing experience to operate intuitive operation digital drawing, which is easy and more interesting to use. This allows the values of conventional drawings to continue while allowing the two types of drawings to compensate each other.

This research discusses four major focuses: 1. Designing a digital drawing system which allows children to easily understand and operate, in order to stimulate their sensitivity towards lines and form observation, continuing the values of conventional and digital drawings. 2. Retaining the features of conventional brushes while integrating various brushes into an intuitive operation digital brush. 3. Applying the tactile learning of children, allowing the development and training of sensitive tactile senses. 4. Avoiding excessive configuration or buttons on digital and tangible user interfaces, while

considering both the human engineering principles and usability in exterior design.

DESIGN DEVELOPMENT

By studying the current condition of children drawings, we found that in conventional drawings, children are able to employ various tools and postures to create rich stroke variations (shown in table 1). However, in the use of digital drawing, it is most difficult for users to switch from icon interfaces to strokes. This has made computer-aided drawings seem dull. According to questionnaires done by child drawing research professionals and field study of users, the stroke functions of tangible digital brushes for children are categorized into brush choice (pencil, crayon, and water painting), and brush thickness (thick, medium, and thin). Then by applying state analysis, develop intuitive operation concepts. Also, setting evaluation parameters according to the needs found by investigating current conditions, in order to evaluate the concepts. The final evaluated results are to simplify brush tools and line features, design lines that match the associated thoughts, and applying tactile senses to control the choice of brush quality. By using the multi-dimension shapes, three different line widths could be created through the changing of brush directions.

Brush-holding position	Condition	Reason	Observation Photograph
Holding the brush in a lower position.	(1) Detailed tracing or small pictures. (2) When the brush tip is thin, such as a pencil.	(1) Maximize stability. (2) Small attention areas.	
Holding the brush in the center.	(1) Speed drawing or coloring. (2) Using a crayon.	(1) Fast movements while coloring small areas. (2) Drawing with a lighter force.	
Holding the brush in an upper position.	(1) Coloring large areas. (2) Using paint brushes.	(1) Avoiding hands touching wet paint. (2) Painting and coloring large areas. (3) Fulfilling the need of watching a big area from the top.	

Table 1. Brush-holding position observation.

Figure 2. Brush tip models that draw three thickness levels

CHANGING THE REPRESENTED LINES OF THE BRUSHES

Line design

By using focus groups, we categorized brush characters into brush exterior characters, writing characters, and representative meaning as developing directions, in order to develop the transformation of pencil, crayon, and paint into different lines. Categorize thoughts with KJ categorizing method, picking out the highly categorized ones and concept line that match the recognition abilities of children. The 26 samples include 11 pencils, 6 crayons, and 9 paints. Models were made by CNC to go through line recognition tests.

Line recognition tests

The aim of the test is to see if children are able to apply the clues provided by the different lines to recognize the relative brush tools. The participants include 11 senior class kindergarten students from the kindergarten of Cheng-Kung University (6 boys and 5 girls). Every child was tested for 15 minutes. The meanings of the lines were first explained to the participants. They were guided to touch to compare the relationship between the exterior of the conventional drawing tool and the drawing. The children were allowed to choose the lines that best matched their imaginations and memories (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Lines represented by brushes

INTUITIVE OPERATION MOVEMENT IN CHANGING BRUSH THICKNESS

Brush tip shape brainstorming

The goal of this stage is to come up with brush tip designs using divergence thinking. Focus groups were used to guide brainstorming and discussions. Brush tip shapes created by divergence thinking are then organized by the KJ method to converge into brush tip shapes with great variances.

Participants were six graduate school students from the Industrial Design department at National Cheng-Kung University. They are four females and two males with background knowledge of industrial design, a sense of beauty judgment, the ability of shape design, flexible thinking and creativity. The pre-experiment description takes 5 minutes, brush tip design brainstorming takes 45 minutes, and KJ method takes 30 minutes. The parameters are to be able to draw three different sizes of lines, including thin (red clay), medium (blue clay), thick (yellow clay), to guide participants to brainstorm the relative brush tip shapes (Figure 2). The brainstorming starts from the brush tip that draws thin lines, then move on to the brush tip that draws thick lines, finally to the brush tip that draws medium lines. The purpose of setting this priority is to that after the participants have thought about the thinnest and the thickest lines, it would be easier for them to grasp the medium sized lines. Participants are encouraged to supplement any additional ideas with notes, including the solving the problem of difficult shaping of clay, and ways on to draw. By using a wooden stick as the extended hypothetical brush stick, participants could easily attach the brush tip to the stick to simulate the operation. The material used is chosen to be extra light clay. This type of clay is slightly elastic after blown dry and not easily cracked. On top of that, the small opening absorbs water, which is suitable for the application of picking up paint in the next stage. The ideas of

divergence thinking are categorized into logical and layered groups and the representative forms are picked out.

User focus group method

The goal of this stage is to observe the operation conditions of 4 to 7 year-old children and to select the shapes they favor, in order to unearth the clues for the operation pattern and intuitive operation. The focus group method allows children to touch and observe different shapes of brush tips and draw different lines. The participants were six middle class kindergarteners from the Cheng-Kung University kindergarten including three boys and three girls. Children take turns dipping the brush tips of different sizes into paint. The process was observed and recorded for reactions and conditions. Interviews were done after each stage to find out their evaluations. A 5-minute instruction was given prior to the experiment. The test and the evaluation took approximately 15 minutes each, which came up to approximately 1 hour of experimental time. By observing children operating on different brush tip shapes, we conclude the shapes they prefer. The operation movements show that: 1. Adjusting grip position and height according to the brush tip shape. 2. Changing angles and directions according to the brush tip shape to draw different lines. 3. Selecting the brush tip shape according to the desired line features (such as selecting a broom-shaped brush tip with many thin lines to draw hair or grass). 4. Brush tips with a large surface area result in a stamping movement.

Intuitive operation conception

Through the intuitive operation pattern and movement behavior obtained by observing children using different brush tip shapes and the preferred brush tip shapes, we have developed seven digital brush shape concepts. The concepts are to use the intuitive hand motion during drawing, including (1) brush rotation, (2) grip height, and (3) grip slanting angle, to develop gesture control in the adjusting of brush thickness, in order to provide users with clues of intuitive operation. From previous observations we know that different brush tools result in the change of grip height due to brush features and usage. Therefore, grip height is not listed as

thickness control, but considered in exterior shapes and line configuration. The selected concepts are categorized into brush rotation and grip slanting angles.

The brush rotation concepts include: R1 the pentagon shaped brush tip include three different lengths. By rotating the brush, the user changes the edge length that touches the picture to change the brush thickness. R2 the brush tip with three different length crest lines. By rotating the crest lines touching the pictures, users could draw lines with different thicknesses. The grip slanting concept include two different shapes: A1 is a brush tip with different angled edges on the side. By changing the brush and picture angle, the user touches the side of the pictures to adjust the thickness. A2 is a brush with three different slanting angles and length. Users change the angle between brush and picture to adjust brush thickness; the more slanting the brush, the thicker the line. The models are made by CNC. Every brush tip is able to draw thicknesses of 5mm, 10mm, and 20mm. The length and diameter of each brush is identical (as shown in Figure 3).

Figure 3. The conceptual model of intuitive operation in changing thickness

Operation experiment of each design

The goal of the experiment is to test if children are able to judge line thicknesses by shapes and crest lines, also to see if the changing of movements are fluent. Users were asked to evaluate. The participants were 11 senior class kindergarteners from Cheng-Kung University kindergarten (six boys and five girls). Researchers guide the participants to observe and touch the shape and crest lines of brush tips, and explain the operation manner of each brush to let them operate. Children are able to compare pairs of shapes and forms to see the common and differences. Therefore, pair comparison was used to guide them to select the preferred designs. The tests were done one child at a time, 15 minutes each. The

calculated experiment results show that the concluded design would be A2.

The chosen lines, brush shape, and grip height consideration are used to design the exterior arrangements and functions for a digital brush for children.

DIGITAL BRUSH DESIGN

This system constructs the parameters for the necessary functions of digital drawing systems for children. It focuses on the stroke adjusting function, categorizing the structural components of stroke into line texture and line thickness. The relative system function of line texture is the changing of brush tools. Brush tools include pencil, crayon, and paint. Line thicknesses are categorized into three levels, including thin, medium, and thick. We employ tablet computer as the operation platform and electronic components as input device. Using the Arduino developing edition to integrate with digital brushes, transmitting control messages to the flash software through server proxy platform, transforming user intuitive operation movements into computer-readable data, and obtain feedback through interface design.

MODEL MAKING

Since model making needs to put electronic components into consideration in order to increase the stability of experiments, the original concept of changing brush tools is to grip the representative line position to sense the change. This system is simulated by lightly pressing on the buttons. The exterior is made by CNC (as shown in figure 4), inserting the key for detecting brush tool change into the model. The three axle accelerator for sensing angle changes is fixed at the top of the brush. The three axle accelerator is used to sense the Z axle angle change of the vertical brush, presenting three levels of thickness change.

Figure 4. Digital brush model

OPERATION MANNER

The two factors of brush stroke are line texture and thickness. In this system, line texture is selected by

recognizing different lines to choose between the brush tools by pressing down on the area. Line thickness is selected by observing the crest line length of brush tip shapes and changing the slanting angle of brush grip. The arrangement is referred to the results of current condition investigation, arranging pencil in the lowest position, crayon in the middle, and paint on the top (as shown in figure 5).

Figure 5. Operation manner

1. Selecting pencil 2. Selecting crayon 3. Selecting paint 4. Drawing thin lines 5. Drawing medium thickness lines 6. Drawing thick lines

DESIGN ASSESSMENT

In order to compare the performance difference and subjective satisfaction of the new design and conventional digital drawings, this research has invited participants between ages of 4 to 7 to participate in the operation and performance tests of the system. Experiment observing focuses are categorized into four sections. They are (1) input performance, (2) stroke changing accuracy, (3) stroke richness, and (4) subjective assessment criteria. Participants are 16 kindergarten children from the senior class of the Cheng-Kung University kindergarten, ages 4 to 7 years old with no hand disabilities. Participants are all first time users of the intuitive operation tangible digital brush. Experiment equipment include tangible digital brush models, conventional drawing brushes, HP tablet PCs, and flash to create the experiment interface. Experiment contents include brush tool and thickness changing to measure the time of function change and error rate. System operation experimenting include saving participants' free creations to analyze and compare the use of digital brushes of different operation manners and their stroke richness. Finally, there is a subjective evaluation. The experiment group would be the intuitive operation tangible

digital brush, where the participants use tactile senses to feel the lines to select between brush tools and change gripping angles to adjust thickness. The control group uses conventional icons as the selection interface. Participants click on the screen to select brush tools and thickness.

Prior to the experiments, researchers would first explain the operation of the system to the participants, demonstrate the way it is used, and guide the participants to practice (as shown in figure 6). Since participants are young children, the experiment design are set to be games with levels, in order to lead the participants into using different stroke to draw lines. The experiment questions include games constructed by nine questions, where every question is a quest. First, the screen would show cartoon characters where participants have to observe the strokes and select if they are constructed by pencil, crayon, or paint, and the thickness (thin, medium, or thick).

After observation, participants click on the clock icon on the bottom right of the page to start timing. Upon this, the lines disappear, and participants are to select the same strokes to complete the quest (as shown in figure 7).

Figure 6. Digital brush teaching demonstration and practice

Figure 7. Experiment question sample

The nine quest answers are timed and the pictures saved for further reference of accuracy analysis. Upon completion of the games, system experimenting is proceeded. Participants are to use the system to create freely. The free creations are saved for further analysis. Figure 8 shows the experiment situation.

Figure 8. Experiment situation of experiment and control groups

Upon completing the above experiments, participants were asked of their assessment opinions. The criteria of subjective assessment refers to the goal set for this research, including (1) user friendliness, (2) effectiveness, (3) error rate, (4) memory, (5) entertainment, and (6) will to continue. Every criterion includes 1 to 2 questions, which comes to a total of 9 questions. The main purpose of this assessment is to understand the subjective view and satisfaction of the participants in these six areas of observation. Since participants are children between 4 and 7 years old, with whom the absolute score evaluation system could result in errors due to misunderstanding, the pair comparison method is used instead of absolute scores. Choice reasons are verbally questioned.

RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

Put experiment data through three-factor repeated measures ANOVA, using Bonferroni to compare and analyze differences between the average numbers in order to identify significant differences in input performance and error rate between the different operation manners. Stroke richness is analyzed using the t test, and subjective evaluation is analyzed using the sign test to test for significant differences in the questions between experiment and control groups.

INPUT PERFORMANCE

In terms of input performance, we can see that intuitive operation performs better than icon interface. There is significant correlation between the three factors of manner, brush, and thickness ($p=0.044$, $p<0.05$), further analysis shows the effect results of the factors under different conditions:

a. In terms of manners: (1) In the use of pencil and paint to draw thin lines, intuitive input performance is significantly better than icon interface ($p=0.000$,

$p < 0.01$) . (2) In the use of paint to draw medium sized lines, intuitive input performance is significantly better than icon interface ($p = 0.009$, $p < 0.01$) . (3) IN the use of crayon to draw thick lines, intuitive input performance is significantly better than icon interface ($p = 0.001$, $p < 0.01$) . (4) In the use of pencil to draw medium and thick lines, and in the use of paint to draw thick lines, there is no significance in input performance between the two operation manners.

b. In terms of brushes: (1) In the use of intuitive operation to draw thick lines, the brush changing movement shows longer time for pencil compared to crayon and paint; there is no significance between crayon and paint. (2) In the use of icon interface to draw thick lines, the brush changing movement shows longer time for pencil and paint, in which the time to click on crayon is significantly longer than paint.

In terms of thickness: (1) In the use of intuitive operation with pencils, it takes longer time to adjust the brush to draw medium lines as compared to thick and thin lines, amongst which, the time to adjust the brush to draw thick lines is significantly longer than adjusting to thin lines ($p = 0.009$, $p < 0.01$) . (2) In the use of intuitive operation with paint, there is no significant difference in the operation time of changing between the three thicknesses. (3) In the use of icon interface to select pencils or paints, it takes longer to select the thin line icon as compared to selecting the medium and thick lines, amongst which, the time for selecting the thin line icon is significantly longer than selecting the thick line. Speculations are that target size affects moving time (Fitt's law).

Amongst the nine operation quests, apart from medium pencil lines which shows no improve in performance, and thick pencil lines which show a decrease in performance, the remainder seven quests have shown an increase of performance. Amongst which, thin pencil lines show the largest increase of performance, while thin and thick crayon lines, thin and medium paint lines all showed an increase of performance of more than 40%.

ACCURACY

In terms of accuracy in stroke switching, as a whole, there is no significant effect between different types

of brush on accuracy. This could be due to the correlation concealing the effect. Therefore, the simple main effect test is required to test for conditions for the independent variable to show an effect on accuracy.

A significant difference is shown in the accuracy rate between the three levels of thicknesses. The accuracy levels go from thin line to thick line to medium line, amongst which the thin lines are significantly more accurate than the medium lines.

Further analysis results of the correlation show that:

a. In terms of style: (1) In the drawing of thin lines, intuitive operation showed higher accuracy than icon interface ($p = 0.015$, $p < 0.05$) . (2) In the drawing of medium and thick lines, there was no significant difference.

b. In terms of brush: (1) The drawing of thick crayon lines is more accurate than the drawing of thick pencil lines. (2) The drawing of thin and medium crayon lines showed no significant difference in accuracy between the three types of brushes.

c. In terms of thickness: (1) Intuitive operation brush presented the highest accuracy in thin lines, then thick lines, and the lowest accuracy with medium lines. (2) There is no significant difference in accuracy between the three line thicknesses drawn using icon interface. (3) When drawing with pencils, thin lines presented a higher accuracy rate than medium and thick lines. This is conforms to the role of pencil in drawing thin lines in conventional drawing situations. (4) When drawing with crayons, thick lines presented a higher accuracy rate than medium lines. (5) When drawing with paint, thin lines presented a higher accuracy rate than medium lines.

In terms of accuracy in changing brush functions, the better items are pencil thin lines, crayon thin lines, paint thin lines, and paint thick lines.

STROKE RICHNESS

When using intuitive operation, the frequency of changing strokes is significantly higher than icon interface. The stroke richness is in turn increased.

SUBJECTIVE EVALUATION

Even though there is no statistical significance in difference between the question items of the two types of brushes, we can see from the average

number that: (1) With the items of entertainment and will to continue, intuitive operation is preferred by participants. (2) With the items of brush changing, the performance and accuracy of intuitive operation are preferred. (3) With items of thickness changing speed and brush tool memory, there was no significant difference. (4) With usage friendliness, line thickness change, and memory, icon interface was preferred.

DISCUSSION

INPUT PERFORMANCE

Experiment results show that input performance as a whole has improved for intuitive operation as compared to icon interface. The reason for this improvement, as shown by the analysis of results, is that drawing thin lines with any brush tool under intuitive operation presented a shorter operation reaction time than icon interface.

Take thin pencil lines for example, there is a 60% increase in performance under intuitive operation as compared to icon interface. The reason for this may be that since pencil is used to draw thin lines in conventional drawing, and intuitive digital brushes allows users to input in similar ways as gripping a conventional pencil instead of clicking on icons, hence increasing the selection speed. The improvement of performance allows users to concentrate on the procedure of drawing (Lai, Li-Ju, 2009).

In the drawing of thick lines under intuitive operation, pencil took the most time amongst the three types of brushes. Also, when drawing with a pencil, selecting medium lines took longer time than selecting thick or thin lines, amongst which, the time to select thick lines is significantly longer than selecting thin lines. The predicted reason being that under intuitive operation using pencils, the gripping position is at the bottom of the brush; since the slanting angle of the brush needs to increase in medium and thick line drawings, the movement is obstructed by the hand, causing participant to change posture to move up on the brush, hence increasing selection time. These results provide reference for future designs to improve on the slanting angle changing range under thickness

adjustment, in order to increase on operation fluency.

There is no significant difference in operation time for thickness selection for painting brushes. The predicted reason is that the gripping position is higher up, which results in less interruption for the change of slanting angles.

The control group shows circles of three different sizes as representative icons of thicknesses. Users are required to click on the icon to switch between functions. Since target size affects selection time (Fitt's law) the performance of drawing thick lines may improve. Therefore, experiment results only show that when drawing thick lines with a crayon, the performance under intuitive operation is significantly better than icon interface.

ACCURACY

In terms of stroke selection accuracy as a whole, there was no significant effect of brush types on accuracy, while the affecting factor being the thickness selection movements. In terms of intuitive operation, a significant difference in accuracy on the operation of three thickness levels was shown. The level of accuracy decreased from thin lines, to thick lines, to medium lines. As for drawing thin lines, intuitive operation showed a higher accuracy than icon interface. In the drawing of medium and thick lines, there was no significant difference in accuracy. In terms of intuitive operation digital brush, the speculated reason for these results are that when the slanting angle is within the central range, it makes operation unstable; while a small slanting angle increases stability, hence decreases the error rate in detailed drawings (Miyahara, Piek, & Barrett, 2008).

STROKE RICHNESS

Upon analyzing the free drawings made by the participants, we found that the stroke richness under intuitive operation is significantly higher than that of conventional icon interface. On average, every child was able to draw with at least three types of strokes, showing that intuitive operation interface allows users to change strokes easily without the distraction of leaving the picture to click on icons. This significantly improves the situation with the icon

interface in which users tend to use only one type of brush. Lines with thickness variations increases the dimensions of the picture, hence increase satisfaction (Hu, 1986).

SUBJECTIVE ANALYSIS

The performance and error rate of the two systems not only undergo objective experiments, but also subjective opinions, in order to obtain information on user opinions of the systems. For example, in terms of function selection accuracy as a whole, the experiment data shows no significant difference between the two systems while participants felt that it is more accurate to select brush with tactile recognition and less accurate to select thickness with slanting angle adjustment. This shows that the possible reason for the decrease of accuracy lies in the change of slanting angles to adjust thickness. The speculated reason is that participants judge line thickness by observing the brush tip shape and crest line, in order to select the appropriate sections of crest lines. However, the program is set with three levels of variation, including thin, medium, and thick, which do not match the expected angles of the participants. This means that participants may expect the slanting angle to be enough to switch to the next thickness, while the system does the change. This is why the error rate for the medium lines is higher than that of the thin and thick lines. Participants were entirely first time users of the digital brush, while most of them had previous experience in digital drawing with a mouse and icon interface. Participants thought that the conventional drawing system used in the control group is easier to use. The speculated reason for this is that the digital brush is bigger in size than the conventional touch screen pens, as well as pressing keys to select functions requires pressing down strength, which causes inconvenience. Also the control group icon interface has been simplified with only the required functions on the screen, causing the icons to be bigger and clearer than the current software interfaces, resulting in an increase in satisfaction for the conventional digital drawing system. Participants expressed in the subjective evaluation that intuitive operation is more interesting than the conventional one and are willing to use it frequently. This is an important goal for the development of this

system. Since the system is design for children between 4 to 7 years of age, it is more important to be able to allow children to draw happily with the system than to increase performance and accuracy.

CONCLUSION

Using different line patterns to represent different brushes allows children to touch and feel, which decreases the time wasted in moving and clicking, also increases operation entertainment and stimulates tactile senses and development. By touching and observing 3-dimensional shapes to judge line thickness is faster than visually judging icon shapes, which in turn increases operation efficiency. Different brush tool representing line patterns are arranged on the brush from top to bottom. This is arranged according to the hand movement positions of using each brush tool. For example, the gripping position is higher when using paint, which is easier to adjust the slanting angle when coloring large areas. The slanting angle is also an intuitive operation movement. Users tent to naturally move the hand to the top of the brush in order to tilt the brush to draw thicker lines. When a thin line is wanted, the hand moves towards the front and the lower end of the brush. In reality, it is true that paint is more suitable for thick lines and pencils for thin lines. According to experiment and discussion, this research concluded the following five conclusions including fluency, accuracy, and delight during use as our focus and goals. (1) The intuitive operation digital brush increases the stroke changing performance of children during digital drawing activities. The increase of performance allows concentration during drawing and avoids the distraction caused by complicated function interface. Preschoolers and school-aged children between 4 to 7 years old are still developing their recognition abilities. The intuitive operation digital brush employs the visual and tactile learning ability of this stage, helps with the increase of efficiency. (2) The intuitive function operation integrates with shape syntax to communicate presumed functions, allowing children to fluently change strokes. The shape designs of digital brushes should consider human engineering as well as shape syntax. This helps

children familiarize and memorize operations. (3) Using intuitive operation to increase line richness. From the observing children making conventional drawings, we saw that they often mix different drawing tools to make rich variations. The brush designed in this research is easy to operate which helps increase the fluency of switching strokes, creating lines with emotional tensions to help express their thoughts and increase the sense of achievement. (4) Children have more fun using the intuitive operation digital brush, which increases willingness to use it. The intuitive operation brush helps improve the difficulties children have with conventional digital drawings, allowing the strength of conventional drawings to expand onto digital drawing.

Suggestions for future researches: (1) Grip slanting angle should be adjusted according to brush tools. The slanting angle used to control thicknesses has programmed the same angle for the three types of brush, while in operation performances, the thick pencil lines result in longer time. Even though it matches the conditions of the conventional brush, the functions are expanded in the world of digital drawing, therefore operation manners need to be reconsidered. (2) The tactile recognition brush selecting tool allows users to grip onto the positions directly and select. The brush selecting tool of this system is confined by system stability, hence uses fingers to hold down keys with line patterns to simulate the gripping action. However, it requires users to hold the keys down to draw, which can cause possible discomfort with the prickly lines. (3) Using wireless brushes. During the drawing procedures we found that wires obstruct operation by distracting users in the adjusting of wires. Hence we suggest future designers to employ Bluetooth models to improve fluency.

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